

End report

'Mass Online Experiments (task 3.4)' of the ODISSEI Roadmap project

Arnout van de Rijt & Rense Corten, 31 Oct 2022, version 1

1 Overview

The ODISSEI acronym stands for Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations. ODISSEI is made up of more than forty [member organisations](#) that financially contribute to its development. These member organisations include Social Science Faculties, Economics Faculties, Research Institutes, Public Research Agencies, Statistics Netherlands, and E-Infrastructure providers. The organisations in ODISSEI represent more than 5,000 social science researchers and ODISSEI aims to support their research by providing world class data infrastructure services that increase their access to data, computing tools, expertise, and financial resources.

Through ODISSEI, researchers have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections as well as innovative and diverse new forms of data. These can be linked to administrative data at Statistics Netherlands (CBS). Combining data from a wide range of sources enables researchers to answer new, exciting, interdisciplinary research questions and to investigate existing questions in novel, new ways.

This is the end report of the task Mass Online Experiments (task 3.4), which was executed as part of the [ODISSEI Roadmap project](#) (NWO grant number 184.035.014) between 1 July 2020 and 31 December 2021. The task leaders were Arnout van de Rijt (UU) and Rense Corten (UU). For more information, please contact info@odissei-data.nl.

2 Task highlights

2.1 Initial problem statement and goal

Social theories posit relationships between conditions and outcomes at the level of *populations*, drawing on causal mechanisms pertaining to interactions among *members*. The holy grail of empirical investigation is therefore the ability to conduct “population experiments” by somehow systematically varying conditions and measuring outcomes at the level of populations while examining member interactions. With modern communication advances, this is now within reach.

The ultimate goal of the ODISSEI Mass Online Experiments initiative is to build a platform that can support experiments on large-scale networked populations of human participants. High quality infrastructure would support researchers in executing cutting-edge research and providing further insights into networked lives and their increasing impact on wider society. The platform is to be used by interested scientists, with a developer assisting in use tailored to user research hypotheses. Developing such a platform implies a number of challenges:

- The development of a backend that can support the real-time volume of traffic of dyadic interactions between thousands of participants.
- Setting up an infrastructure of hosting and technical support
- For running experiments with Dutch participants: setting up an infrastructure for recruitment and payment of participants.

The current grant provides too little funding to achieve all this. At the same time, existing software and platforms could potentially serve as a starting point for the imagined platform. The goal of this task therefore twofold:

1. To create an inventory of existing software, tools, and platforms for online experimentation and assess their usability as a starting point for setting up a platform for mass experimentation in the Netherlands;
2. To prepare a proof of concept in the form of three example studies that demonstrate the usefulness of online mass experiments, accompanied by professional illustrations that speak to the imagination.

2.2 Intended deliverables at the end of the project

After thoughtful consideration, it was agreed to change the scope of the project and focus on two rather than three) studies that demonstrate the usefulness of online mass experiments. Those two example studies were designed to push the boundaries of what has been previously delivered in terms of scale and complexity and served as a departure point for the evaluation of the technical setup that is needed for building a “plug-and-play” platform for conducting mass online experiments.

1. The first study (conducted in collaboration with colleagues at RUG) directly builds on an earlier study that focused on the spread of fake news throughout the network that includes

echo chambers in their structure (Nunner et al. 2021¹). In the follow-up study that is executed within this task, the researchers will focus on establishing whether interventions may effectively inhibit the spread of fake news. To this end reputation systems will be introduced that provide veracity scores for users and content. Such interventions may backfire in polarized settings, is the assumption.

2. The second study (conducted in collaboration with colleagues at UJ) will introduce network dynamics and apply it to the question of the effects of disease avoidance on social cohesion.

Those studies will rely on the same software platform (Elixir) and will serve to 1) illustrate the broad scope of applications and research questions that can be studied using a platform for mass experimentation, and 2) explore the technical limitations of the platform developed. Developing the software further into a platform that can be easily applied by other researchers (i.e., including documentation and structural support) is beyond the current proof-of-concept and would require additional funding.

2.3 Layman summary

A key challenge in social science is understanding how macro-level social phenomena – e.g., social inequality, network structure, or polarization – emerge as consequences of the actions of many interacting individuals. Yet, typical empirical strategies available to social scientists often fall short of meeting this challenge. On the one hand, survey data provide rich information about the attributes and opinions of individuals, but little about their interactions. Controlled laboratory experiments, on the other hand, allow for studying causal mechanisms of social interaction in detail, but lack the scale to represent the fundamental complexity of social life. Mass online experiments – in which more than 100 people interact via online interfaces - offer a solution as they allow for studying both micro level behavior and the emergence of social phenomena at scale under controlled conditions. However, such experiments require specific skills and tools that are in short supply in the social sciences and humanities, leading to high fixed costs as a barrier to ground-breaking research. The project addresses these issues by establishing a proof of concept for Mass Online Experiments and the deployment of such experiments for the general social science community in the Netherlands.

3 Task end report

3.1 Conclusions

The task members have evaluated the application of the various software platforms that are available in the market to conduct online mass experiments. Their conclusion was that the functionalities of ELIXIR are sufficient for the execution of the studies that are envisioned within this task but there are limited possibilities for expanding this functionality into a “plug-and-play” principle, where the researchers would be offered a platform that would allow them design the execute the experiments based on the ready solutions. The team has also explored also other available platforms and their functionalities. An expansion of the oTree software is one of the new directions to be explored in the future round of funding applications (for details, see the *Future funding* section).

¹ Nunner, Hendrik, Vincent Buskens, Rense Corten, and Mirjam Kretschmar. 2021. 'Effects of Risk Perception on Epidemics in a Small-World Network Game'. Working paper. Utrecht University.

With the three applications successfully completed, the task has clearly indicated its value for scientific breakthroughs. The results of the studies are summarized below.

The first study (by Jonas Stein, RUG) focused on the spread of fake news and the role of reputation systems in this process. An emergent approach (e.g. Twitter's Birdwatch) was to harness the wisdom of the crowd by enabling recipients of an online message on a social media platform. In this way, the social media users could attach veracity assessments to it, with the intention to allow poor initial crowd reception to temper belief in and further spread of misinformation. The authors studied this approach by letting 4,000 subjects in 80 experimental bipartisan communities sequentially rate the veracity of informational messages. They find that in well-mixed communities, the public display of earlier veracity ratings indeed enhances the correct classification of true and false messages by subsequent users. But when false information is sequentially rated in strongly segregated communities, crowd intelligence backfires. This happens because early raters' ideological bias, which is aligned with a message, influences later raters' assessments away from the truth. These results identify an important problem for community misinformation detection systems and suggest that platforms must somehow compensate for the deleterious effect of echo chambers in their design.

The second study (by Henrik Hunner, UU) focused on how disease avoidance may come at the cost of social cohesion and it again used insights from a large-scale social networking experiment. The underlying assumption in this study was the notion that avoidance behavior is a typical behavioral adaptation during times of increased health risks. The resulting disruption of social networks may fundamentally change the course of an epidemic, but less is known about the extent to which people adapt their behavior and to what extent this changes the dynamics of disease spread. To study the feedback loop between avoidance behavior, social networks, and the spread of infectious diseases, the researchers executed "Networking during Infectious Diseases Task" (NIDM), a part of an incentivized game-theoretic experiment that rewards maintaining social relations and structures and penalizes acquiring infections. Data collected from a large-scale ($n = 2,879$) online experiment reveals that disease avoidance dominates networking decisions, despite a comparably low penalty for getting infected. As a result, the authors of the study observed low numbers of infections, but also drastic changes in network structure, such as the deterioration of densely connected clusters. These results imply that the focus on a more obvious signal (i.e., disease avoidance) may lead to unwanted and harder to foresee side effects (i.e., loss of social cohesion). Furthermore, this may have a reinforcing effect on loss of well-being through social isolation, an effect that has been observed during the COVID-19 pandemic, and should therefore be considered for the communication of non-pharmaceutical interventions and for the design of measures to maintain social cohesion during epidemics.

Future funding

This proof of concept has been used in the development of the Mass Online Experiment platform which has become a prominent part of the current SSHOC-NL application (submitted to the Large Scale Infrastructure call of NWO). The grant, if awarded, will accelerate access to Mass Online Experiments by embedding them within a national panel and providing the technical and methodological expertise to conduct them. This includes the maturation of a permanent suite of tools for the deployment of Mass Online Experiments and will eliminate the fixed costs associated with such experiments for Dutch researchers. The proposed suite will consist of four components: (1) recruitment of participants from i.a. the LISS panel, Panl, and from respondents samples drawn from CBS, RvIG or through online advertising, (2) A code library of reusable building blocks that allow

participants to interact in a variety of experimental designs programmed in Elixir, Empirica, oTree and Z-tree Unleashed, (3) The durable provision of technical support for researchers in developing experiments by establishing a pool of developers with relevant expertise, (4) The procurement of hardware for experiments. When released, the Mass Online Experiment Tools platform will scale up the existing solutions which will be accessible to the wider SSH community.

As the starting point of this potential application, the team has also applied for the eScience SSI in Social Sciences grant. If awarded, the grant would expand on the oTree functionality (e.g., tools for online experiments) to be widely applicable in the LISS panel. The envisioned output of the project is a well-documented public code base to be used by researchers and panel engineers for developing controlled online panel experiments. It would allow smooth real-time interaction between online experimental interfaces and the data already available from the LISS panel.

3.2 Dissemination activities

The following papers based on the three pilots are published online or are currently under review.

Stein J., Frey V., de Rijt A. 2022. *Realtime user ratings as a strategy for combating misinformation: An experimental study*. Preprint; <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1967510/v1>

The final study (by Henrik Nunner), entitled *Disease avoidance may come at the cost of social cohesion: Insights from a large-scale social networking experiment* has not yet been published but is being presented to a wide public (among other, during the ODISSEI conference for Social Sciences in 2022).

Other work has been also presented during international conferences, for example at the Annual Conference of Experimental Sociology (2021) or the International Sunbelt Social Networks Conference (2022).